

METHODS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF SAMBISTS IN THE TRAINING PROCESS

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Annotation: This article discusses questions about the formation of psychological and anatomical-physiological qualities in young sambo wrestlers, which include: memory, attention, thinking, visual method and emotional state. The article may be useful to coaches and other specialists in the field of physical education and sports.

Key words: sambo, anatomical, physiological and psychological qualities, young sambo wrestlers, psychological preparation.

Introduction. To prepare young sambo wrestlers at the initial stage of their formation, it is necessary to pay special attention to two main points - physical and psychological preparation, since without them it is impossible to design the training process of a teenager and justify the importance of engaging in this sport [1, 2, 3]. Physical and psychological preparation must be carried out comprehensively not only at the initial, but also in subsequent stages of the training process [6, 7, 8]. Due to the close relationship of such factors in the training process, it is possible to conduct specialized trainings, namely: plot-intellectual and psychotechnical games, as well as psychoregulatory training, with the help of which it is possible to ensure the full formation of stability in young sambo wrestlers in receiving various loads during systematic sambo training, as well as education, observance and maintenance of a healthy lifestyle, development of proper motivation during the self-improvement of a teenager [4, 5, 6].

In order to talk about the characteristics of the work and development of the body, it is necessary to define the child's younger age. The younger age of a child is the peculiarities of the anatomical development of the age in which a qualitative stage of change and improvement of all body systems takes place [9, 12, 14]. During this period of development, the most favorable is the formation in children of coordination, dexterity, flexibility, and various physical qualities, which are realized through intense physical activity. To work with this age group, each coach must have in-depth knowledge and knowledge of the anatomy, physiology and psychology of the child [10, 11, 15]. It is at a young age that the health and physical development of the child are closely related to each other during the educational and training process, since at this stage the process of formation and development of the main muscle groups occurs, which in the future will help to master more complex elements and exercises not only in physical education classes , but also in any sport [16, 17].

At the initial stage of the training process, at the age of 10 to 12 years, each organization leader, coach or instructor forms training groups. To do this, it is necessary to know and understand well the basic anatomical, physiological and psychological characteristics of students of this age group. At this age, all muscle groups are formed and developed in adolescents, which is why, with insufficient knowledge and understanding of how the body works, the methods of physical education can lead to big mistakes that will affect the overload of adolescents (children) with subsequent resulting injuries or deterioration of health [18].

Let's stop and analyze the main features of adolescents (children) of the age group 10-12 years, such as: anatomical, physiological and psychological. Some of the indicators of body development in adolescents (children) aged 10-12 years between boys and girls there is no strong difference, since their body proportions are the same, but if we take the strength qualities of the above age group, then girls predominate more because that they undergo an early process of puberty. At this

stage of development of the body in adolescents, the structure of tissues, muscles, height and weight continues to form due to the strengthening of the bone skeleton. To achieve a positive result during the educational and training process in adolescents (children), it is necessary to devote enough time to such a feature as attentiveness. Due to attentiveness, a teenager can easily master this or that technical action or exercise during training. Mindfulness also helps reduce the likelihood of injury during exercise. But due to his adolescence, the student is often distracted and cannot maintain attention on something specific for a long time, so he reacts to various foreign objects, extraneous noise, conversation or shouting. Intense and concentrated attention quickly leads to fatigue in a teenager during classes, training, or when performing any action in everyday life.

Memory in adolescents (children) works somewhat differently than in adults, since children aged 10-12 years focus on the external features of the objects being studied, and not on their semantic essence.

It is necessary to pay special attention to a teenager's memory, which is mechanical in nature, that is, children remember any action or exercise through repeated repetition during the training process. In this regard, in the process of reproducing memorized material, adolescents have a large number of errors and inaccuracies, which is why this material is not retained in memory for a long time. With repeated observations, it was found that adolescents (children) begin to forget the material they have studied during the training process within 2 months. In order to prevent this process, it is necessary to systematically, over a long period of time, repeat the completed educational material with children, as well as arrange control sections and final exams.

Thinking in adolescents (children) aged 10-12 years is different in that it has a close relationship with imagination. At this age, children have difficulty mastering any concepts due to a lack of knowledge about the general laws of nature and society.

That is why in this age group visual observation techniques are more effective than verbal ones.

In adolescence, the visual method plays a major role, since in order to consolidate the knowledge acquired with the help of words, it is necessary to clearly show teenagers the movements for a more positive result. Children's interest in games is associated with vivid emotional experiences.

They are characterized by the following features of emotions: spontaneous character, vivid external expression in facial expressions, movements, exclamations. Children of this age are not yet able to hide their emotional states; they spontaneously succumb to them.

The emotional state changes rapidly both in intensity and character. Children are not able to control and restrain emotions if circumstances require it. These qualities of emotional states, presented to the spontaneous flow, can take hold and become character traits.

Therefore, it is necessary to cultivate stable determination, endurance, initiative, independence, and determination in adolescents. The specificity of physical exercises opens up great opportunities for the education and development of the necessary volitional qualities in children.

Conclusions. To summarize the above, it should be noted that practicing sambo wrestling contributes to the development of anatomical, physiological and psychological characteristics of adolescents (children), which need to be given special attention, since they play an important role in the formation of the athlete's personality and the socialization of the teenager in society.

References:

1. Ustoev, A. K., & Babarahmatov, B. B. (2020). Спорт ўйинларининг ташкилий асосларида кўп йиллик тайёрлов тизими. *Молодой ученый*, (21), 799-801.
2. Ustoev, A. K. (2021). Development of speed-power abilities in young sambists. *Current research journal of pedagogics*, 2(11), 157-160.
3. Устоев, А. К. (2022). Формирование волевых усилий у подростков в процессе занятий физическим воспитанием. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(1), 14-18.

4. Kurbanovich, U. A. (2022). Ways to Solving Problems in Training Young Kurash Wrestlers. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 108-111.
5. Babarakhmatov, B. B. (2022). Role of the trainer in the psychological training of the athlete in outschool work on physical education and sport. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 2(106), 206-209.
6. Boborakhmatov, B. (2022). Initial training of young athletes in the conditions of a sport class. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(13), 70-74.
7. Boborakhmatov Bobir Buriyevich. (2023, February 28). Features of teaching short running techniques. Youth, science, education: Topical issues, achievements and innovations, Prague, Czech. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7700211>
8. Boboraxmatov, B. B. R. (2022). Yengil atletikachilar organizmiga iqlim omillarining ta'siri. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(9), 338-347.
9. Burievich, B. B. (2022). Role of the Trainer in the Psychological Training of the Athlete in Out-School Work on Physical Education and Sport. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 29–32.
10. Burievich, B. B. (2022). Improvement of Speed and Strength Abilities in Young Middle Distance Runners. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 661-664.
11. Mamasaxatovna, Y. F. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachining innovasion faoliyatini shakllantirish shartlari. *Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 2(1), 134-137.
12. Mamasaxatovna, Y. F. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'limda steam ta'lim texnologiyasidan foydalanish zaruriyati. *Journal of new century innovations*, 2(1), 170-177.
13. Mamasakhatovna, Y. F. (2022). Application of Interactive Board in Teaching Preschool Children. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 79-83.

14. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2020). Взаимосвязь проблем воспитания познавательного интереса и развития мышления в процессе обучения математике. *Вопросы педагогики*, (6-1), 348-351.
15. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2020). Чувства и этические представления дошкольника. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-1), 434-436.
16. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2019). Психологические механизмы воздействия игры на младших школьников. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 240-243.
17. Юлдошева, Ф. М., & Избосарова, З. А. (2018). Особенности развития творческих способностей в дошкольном возрасте. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 117-118.
18. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). The role of the learning and game environment in the formation of volitional qualities in physical education lessons. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(4), 38-45.